

ENRICHMENT AND IMPROVEMENT OF DIET THERAPY FOR CHRONIC HEPATITIS WITH LOCAL PLANT PROTEIN-RICH AND SPECIALIZED DIETARY PRODUCTS

Zokirxodjayev Sherzod Yahyoyevich

Sharafaddinova Gulbahor Rashidovna

Relevance of the topic

Liver diseases, according to the World Health Organization, are widespread globally and have seen a significant increase over the past 20 years. Every year, 2-3 million people are registered with viral, toxic, drug-induced, alcoholic, or autoimmune liver damage. According to WHO statistics for 2018, the number of people living with hepatitis C was 71 million. About 1.5 million new patients are registered annually.

Diet therapy, in combination with pharmacological drugs, plays an important role in the treatment of chronic hepatitis. According to Order No. 74 of the Ministry of Health from 2008, the energy value and calorie content of meals prepared in all hospitals are indicated. However, these are based on the Pevzner diet. Currently, our state's nutrition policy recommends the use of local products in healthy and dietary nutrition, which is economically beneficial.

Throughout human evolution, the digestive system has adapted to assimilate local products. Imported products and their production technologies are not compatible with our lifestyle. The high cost of imported food products (such as buckwheat, pearl barley, barley, Russian peas, seafood, etc.) has led to their limited use in dietary therapy. Through the evolutionary process, it has been established that local foods, particularly grains, are absorbed much better by the digestive organs. It is effective to enrich the breakfast portion of the diet with holvaytar (a sweet made from chickpea flour) and specialized dietary products. Chickpea flour contains more protein, vitamins, and trace elements, which increase the body's immunobiological resistance. The use of modern and dietary nutrition in the prevention and treatment of chronic liver diseases, and the development of diets aimed at increasing patients' immunity, are among the urgent tasks facing medicine today. It is especially important to follow a dietary regimen, consume food in small portions, and add foods rich in plant fiber to the diet. These include vegetables, fruits, and grains. For the same purpose, it is recommended to adjust the ratio between plant and animal proteins to 50/50%. Plant proteins have high biological value. Individualized nutrition is the most important part of complex therapy for chronic hepatitis. Usually, dietary nutrition is prescribed in combination with other types of therapy (such as pharmacological preparations, physiotherapeutic procedures, etc.).

Research objectives

1. Develop a weekly menu incorporating Holvaytar, a diet food rich in plant protein, and a specialized dietary biologically active product from the "Yuma bio" group into the diet to improve diet therapy for chronic hepatitis.

2. Study the clinical and immunological states and protein metabolism in patients with chronic hepatitis when given Holvaytar, a diet food rich in plant protein, as part of their diet therapy.

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3. Investigate the effectiveness of changes in clinical, immunological, and protein metabolism when a specialized dietary biologically active product is included in the diet of patients with chronic hepatitis.

4. Examine changes in clinical, immunological, and protein metabolism during diet therapy when Holvaytar, a diet food rich in plant protein prepared from local Central Asian chickpea flour, is given for breakfast along with a specialized dietary supplement.

5. Study the state of proper nutrition in patients with chronic hepatitis based on a questionnaire and determine the body mass index according to World Health Organization recommendations.

Scientific novelty

1. Develop a dietary regimen for chronic hepatitis treatment that enhances the effectiveness of diet therapy by incorporating a breakfast rich in local plant proteins and a specialized dietary supplement.

2. In the diet therapy of chronic hepatitis, the clinical, immunological, and protein metabolism indicators are studied following the inclusion of a plant-based protein-rich dietary dish called holvaytar, prepared from local Central Asian pea flour, in the breakfast ration.

3. In the diet therapy of patients with chronic hepatitis, changes in clinical, immunological, and protein metabolism indicators are studied when specialized food supplements are included in the diet.

4. In diet therapy, clinical, immunological, and protein metabolism changes are studied when the dietary dish holvaytar, rich in local plant protein prepared from Central Asian pea flour, is combined with a specialized dietary supplement for breakfast.

The study subjects were patients with chronic hepatitis in the gastroenterology department of the multidisciplinary clinic of the Khorezm region and in the therapy department of the Urgench branch clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy.

The blood and serum of patients were taken as the subject of the study for immunological research and determination of biochemical changes.

Research methods

Clinical studies (general laboratory, biochemical-ALT, AST, bilirubin) total protein, albumin, fibrinogen, cytokines IL-2, IL-6, IL-17, immunoglobulins A, M, G, immunological CD-3, CD-4, CD-8, TNF, fibroscan, ultrasound, MSCT and statistical methods are used.

During our research work, we studied the chemical composition of Central Asian chickpea flour and wheat flour intended for use in diet therapy, and compared the following results. We can see the comparison results in Table 1.

Table 1

Nutritional value	Chickpea flour	Wheat flour
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Calorie content, kcal	328.6	334.0
Proteins	20.1	10.3
Fats	4.32	1.1
Carbohydrates	46.1	68.9
Dietary fiber	9.9	0.1
Water	14.0	14.5
Starch	42.9	62.3
Mono and disaccharides	2.96	0.2
Minerals	3.0	0.5

The results in this table show that chickpea flour contains 9.8 times more proteins, which are important for the treatment of chronic hepatitis, than wheat flour. It also contains 9.8 times more dietary fiber, 2.76 times more mono- and disaccharides, and 2.5 times more minerals.

In conclusion, as can be seen from the analysis of the chemical and nutritional value of chickpea flour in Table 1, it contains sufficient amounts of all beneficial substances. 100 g of the product contains 20.1 g of protein, 4.32 g of fat, and 46.1 g of carbohydrates. The mineral content in chickpea flour is higher than in wheat flour. Most importantly, it is distinguished by its richness in vitamins B₁, B₂ and PP, as well as its high energy content.

The proteins, fats, calcium, vitamins B₁ and B₂, and minerals contained in chickpea flour are important in increasing the body's resistance to viruses.

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